

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, R. Chelsea Nagy, & Alison K. Post

Lava flow on Mauna Loa
(Credit: [USGS photo Kendra J. Lynn](#))

Quick Updates

- Several new papers were published by Earth Lab researchers and affiliates, including: "[Ten simple rules for working with high resolution remote sensing data](#)" by 20 current and former Earth Lab members, and "[Fuel connectivity, burn severity, and seedbank survivorship drive ecosystem transformation in a semiarid shrubland](#)" by Adam Mahood, Michael Koontz, and Jennifer Balch.
- Natasha Stavros, Analytics Hub Director, appeared in an episode of the [Eyes on Earth](#) podcast to discuss using [ECOSTRESS](#) data to predict burn severity.
- James Rattling Leaf Sr., ESIL Tribal Liaison, spoke at The White House Office Of Science And Technology Policy discussion addressing a 10-year research strategy to respond to global change.
- Join our weekly [EDS seminar series](#) to collaborate with professionals and learn about the use of *big data* to advance knowledge of the dynamics and interactions of the Earth system, towards actionable insights and tools. [Sign up](#) to join our email list.

Sensing the Earth Summit

In November, Earth Lab partnered with the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (AIHEC), Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIIL), National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), Ecological Forecasting Initiative, and The Carpentries to conduct a 2-day environmental data science workshop at Haskell Indian Nations University in Lawrence, KS. Earth Lab team members led hands-on training sessions about retrieving and plotting LiDAR imagery and accessing local climate and geospatial data. See the descriptions below for more details about the workshops.

In addition, Jim Sanovia, an enrolled tribal member of the Rosebud Sioux Tribe and ESIIL Tribal Resilience Data Scientist, presented about his experience participating in Earth Lab's Earth Data Science Corps (EDSC) with his students as a former faculty member at Oglala Lakota College. He identified the incorporation of Earth Data Science, integrated with data sovereignty and management, as an essential next step when partnering with Tribal entities.

EDS with Python - Nate Quarderer

[Nate](#) walked participants through a demonstration that was modeled after the Earth Data Science Corps and [ESIIL Stars](#) programs. Using a cloud-based Jupyter Notebook, participants learned how to open and plot a LiDAR image of the Haskell Indian Nations University campus using Python. Participants were able to see in high resolution culturally important campus features. (View the demo [here](#)).

LiDAR/Hillshade
Image of Haskell
Indian Nations
University (0.5m)

Climate Futures Toolbox [CFT] with R - Ty Tuff

In [Ty's](#) workshop, participants learned how to access cloud-based geospatial data from the OpenStreetMap API to generate a basemap of the area surrounding Haskell. Ty then demonstrated a local application of the CFT that looked at future climate patterns under different scenarios giving participants a window into what to expect for future temperature, precipitation, and humidity trends around Haskell (Lawrence, KS). (View the demo [here](#)).

"Getting decision-support tools into the hands of TCU faculty, staff, and students will be the best way to not only see what works, but to know where the next steps are for innovation and large-scale adoption and implementation... the relationships we're building are what matters most, and these partnerships are more than just building skills and technical competence, it's how we're going to survive."

- Patrick A Freeland, Livelihoods Knowledge Exchange Network

AGU Conference Participation

Several team members presented their research at the American Geophysical Union annual Fall conference. The annual conference took place December 12-16th, 2022 in Chicago with an option to attend virtually. Elsa Culler, Jennifer Balch, & Nate Quarderer presented posters of their research. Chelsea Nagy, Matt Rossi, Max Cook gave oral presentations. Additionally, Jennifer Balch gave an invited lecture to present her research: 'Warming weakens the night-time barrier to global fire'.

New Team Members

Earth Lab is growing! Since our last newsletter we've gained two new members who will both take part in creating the quarterly newsletter. See our introductory Q&A session of our new team members below.

Alison Post is the Program Manager for Earth Lab

1. What is your background?

I completed a PhD in Ecology studying climate change in grasslands. Most recently, I was a postdoc with the PhenoCam Network - a collection of digital cameras (>700 across the world) that take regular pictures of diverse ecosystem canopies to monitor patterns and changes.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

I'm excited to meet and collaborate with researchers across many different disciplines and agencies to advance climate change research.

3. What is your favorite national park?

Yellowstone (cliche, but for a good reason).

Casey Jensen is the Program Assistant for Earth Lab

1. What is your background?

I completed my B.A in Environmental Science & Graphic Design where I focused on ecological research & invasive species. Most recently, I was conducting research on invasive species & their evolutionary biogeography in Oahu, Hawaii.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

I'm looking forward to collaborating with our team & Earth Lab's network & to help advance science on a professional level.

3. What is your favorite national park?

Hawai'i Volcano Park. The landscape & culture at this park are indescribable.

ESIL Innovation Summit

ESIL is hosting the first Innovation Summit in May 2023 and will build the network of environmental data scientists through plenary talks, breakout sessions, and networking opportunities. There will also be an optional training session beforehand (May 22, 2023) for participants who want to learn basic data science skills (e.g., programming, data and code sharing best practices). While the application for the Summit has closed, there are still opportunities to participate in other ESIL activities. Please contact esiil@colorado.edu for more information.